

A Privacy-Preserving System for Border Crossing and Inspection

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Abstract—This paper presents a privacy-preserving system for border crossing and inspection composed of two Android applications: the Pre-Registration App and the Border Guard App. The system enables travelers to manage their trips, pre-capture document data and biometrics on their own devices, and perform on-device quality and verification checks before securely transmitting this information to the Border Guard App via a peer-to-peer (P2P) channel. The Pre-Registration App supports Machine Readable Zone (MRZ) scanning, Near Field Communication (NFC) passport chip reading, Open Face Image Quality (OFIQ) assessment, Single and Differential Morphing Attack Detection (S-MAD and D-MAD), face similarity verification using the FaceNet algorithm, and a European Blockchain Services Infrastructure (EBSI) verifiable credential (VC) that can later be verified by border authorities. Communication between the two apps occurs via WiFi Direct after a Quick Response (QR) code handshake, ensuring that no personal data is transmitted before arrival at the Border Control Point (BCP). The Border Guard App performs additional biometric matching and document authentication and presents the verification results along with the traveler’s passport information to the border guard for final inspection. The key outcome is that the system reduces waiting times at BCPs through pre-arrival registration and enables better personnel management through expected arrival tracking.

Index Terms—privacy-preserving AI, edge computing, Android applications, border inspection system, biometric authentication

I. INTRODUCTION

Modern border control systems face increasing pressure from growing international travel volumes while maintaining security standards.¹ Traditional border crossing procedures require travelers to queue for document verification, biometric capture, and security checks, leading to significant delays and congestion at BCPs. This paper presents a novel two-application system that mitigates these challenges by reducing overall waiting times at BCPs while upholding high security standards through privacy-preserving pre-registration and secure communication protocols.

The system comprises two Android applications: the *Pre-Registration App* used by travelers, and the *Border Guard App* used by border control officers. Together, they streamline the border crossing process, support real-time verification, and enhance privacy and security through P2P communication.

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¹According to the Statistical Office of the Republic of Slovenia, air passenger traffic increased significantly in recent years. Source: <https://www.stat.si/StatWeb/en/news/Index/13546>

I-A. Pre-Registration App

The Pre-Registration App enables travelers to complete the necessary steps for border crossing ahead of time. Users can create a profile, register a future trip by selecting the intended date, time, and BCP, and manage trips (edit or delete). When the time comes to cross the border, the traveler can transmit the pre-registration data directly to the border guard.

To enable secure and reliable identity verification during pre-registration, the application incorporates a multimodal set of biometric and document authentication techniques. These processes ensure that the data transmitted to border authorities is both accurate and trustworthy. The technologies integrated into the app include:

- MRZ scanning
- NFC passport chip reading
- OFIQ assessment
- Face similarity verification using FaceNet
- S-MAD
- D-MAD
- EBSI VCs

I-B. Border Guard App

The Border Guard App is used by officers to validate the identity and intent of travelers at the border. Upon receiving the data from the traveler, the officer captures a live facial photo of the individual, verifies the quality of the image, and performs a face similarity check against the photos received during pre-registration. In parallel, the officer also asserts the authenticity and validity of the traveler’s digital credentials according to EBSI.

To support these procedures, the app incorporates the following technologies:

- OFIQ assessment
- Face similarity verification using FaceNet
- EBSI VC verification

These checks provide an additional layer of security and ensure that the traveler presenting themselves matches the data received via the Pre-Registration App.

I-C. Communication Between Applications

Because both biometric data and identity documents are considered highly sensitive, the system employs a secure P2P communication protocol for data exchange between the two

applications. This approach eliminates the need for centralized data storage and preserves privacy.

To establish this secure channel, the following technologies are used:

- QR code generation and scanning (for initial handshake)
- WiFi Direct protocol (for encrypted and secure P2P communication)

This method ensures that the information is transferred directly from the traveler to the border guard, maintaining high confidentiality and security levels.

II. RELATED WORK

Previous work in border control systems has predominantly relied on specialized hardware infrastructure installed at BCPs. Traditional systems require dedicated passport scanners, professional biometric capture devices, and fingerprint readers that are only available at the physical border crossing locations. Such systems demand substantial investment in infrastructure and limit scalability, as all verification procedures must be conducted on-site upon the traveler’s arrival.

In contrast, the approach proposed in this paper enables the pre-registration process to be completed using the traveler’s own Android device. Travelers can perform document scanning, biometric capture, and verification steps prior to departure, using only the built-in camera and NFC functionality of standard consumer smartphones.

II-A. Alternative pre-screening techniques

Some recent approaches have explored alternative methods for traveler identification and pre-screening. VehicLens [1] presents an integrated AI system that focuses on soft biometric features such as gender classification and vehicle-specific characteristics like car model identification for border security applications. While such soft biometric approaches can provide auxiliary information for risk assessment, they lack the strong authentication guarantees required for secure border crossings.

Our system adopts a fundamentally different approach by implementing a comprehensive set of hard biometric authentication and verification procedures. These include cryptographic validation of electronic passports, face recognition enhanced with advanced morphing attack detection. Together, these measures provide a level of security comparable to, or exceeding, that of traditional border control systems.

II-B. Morphing attack detection

Research in morphing attack detection has become crucial for securing face recognition systems. Ferrara et al. [2] first demonstrated the susceptibility of these systems to morphed images—synthetic composites that blend facial features from multiple individuals to produce fraudulent identity documents. To mitigate this threat, our system incorporates two state-of-the-art morphing detection approaches. For S-MAD, we utilize the UBO-SMAD-R3 model based on the Revelio framework by Borghi et al. [3], which provides a modular and effective approach using Inception-ResNet V1 architecture. For D-MAD, we implement the double siamese framework proposed

by Borghi et al. [4], which performs deep feature analysis by comparing the document image with a live-captured image.

II-C. Face recognition

The face recognition component of our system is based on FaceNet by Schroff et al. [5], which introduced the concept of learning a unified embedding for face recognition using a deep convolutional network. FaceNet’s ability to map face images to a compact Euclidean space where distances directly correspond to face similarity makes it ideal for mobile deployment while maintaining high accuracy.

II-D. OFIQ

For ensuring the quality of captured facial images, we integrate the OFIQ framework developed by the German Federal Office for Information Security (BSI) [6]. OFIQ serves as the reference implementation for the ISO/IEC 29794-5 international standard for face image quality assessment. The framework provides transparent and detailed quality evaluation of facial images through a comprehensive set of quality metrics including illumination uniformity, image sharpness, facial pose, and background characteristics. Integrating OFIQ into our mobile application ensures that captured facial images comply with international quality standards prior to submission, thereby minimizing the risk of rejection during verification and enhancing the reliability of subsequent biometric matching.

II-E. EBSI

For secure digital identity management, we integrate with the EBSI [7], which provides a decentralized framework for verifiable credentials. This integration enables travelers to maintain control over their identity data while providing cryptographic proof of authenticity to border authorities.

The key innovation of our work lies in the combination of these technologies into a privacy-preserving, mobile-first architecture that eliminates the need for specialized hardware at BCPs while maintaining or exceeding the security standards of traditional systems. By shifting the computational burden to travelers’ devices and performing verification locally, we achieve both scalability and privacy preservation, addressing two critical challenges in modern border management.

III. SYSTEM WORKFLOW

The proposed system operates through two distinct workflows: the pre-registration process completed by travelers on their personal devices and the border crossing process that facilitates secure data transfer and verification at BCPs. This section details both workflows showcasing the full system pipeline.

III-A. Pre-Registration Process Pipeline

The pre-registration process enables travelers to complete document verification and biometric capture before arriving at the BCP. This comprehensive pipeline ensures data quality and authenticity through multiple validation stages, as illustrated in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. Detailed flowchart illustrating the complete registration process workflow in the Pre-Registration App, including MRZ scanning, NFC passport chip reading, facial image capture with OFIQ assessment, FaceNet-based similarity verification, S-MAD and D-MAD morphing detection, and EBSI verifiable credential issuance.

The process begins with **MRZ scanning**, where travelers use their device camera to capture the MRZ area of their passport. The application extracts key information including document number, date of birth, and expiration date. This information is essential for initiating the NFC chip reading process, as a passport chip's Basic Access Control (BAC), a security feature that encrypts data on the e-passport's RFID chip, requires the reader to use MRZ information to enable access.

Following successful MRZ extraction, the system initiates **NFC passport chip reading**. Travelers place their NFC-

enabled passport against their device to establish communication with the embedded chip. The application reads the digitally signed data stored on the chip, including the holder's photograph and additional biographical details. This step provides cryptographic validation of the document's authenticity and verifies consistency between the chip data and the previously extracted MRZ information.

The next phase involves **facial image capture and OFIQ assessment**. Travelers use their device's front-facing camera to take a live selfie, which is then immediately evaluated using the OFIQ framework. This assessment analyzes multiple quality metrics, including illumination uniformity, image sharpness, facial pose alignment, and background characteristics. If the image fails to meet the required standards, the application provides real-time feedback, prompting the user to retake the photo to ensure optimal conditions for subsequent biometric processing.

Once a high-quality facial image is obtained, the system performs **FaceNet-based face similarity verification**. Using FaceNet's deep neural network embeddings, the application compares the captured selfie against the passport photograph read from the NFC chip. This process produces a similarity score that indicates the likelihood that both images represent the same individual, serving as an initial biometric authentication step.

The system then performs **S-MAD** using the UBO-SMAD-R3 model. This process analyzes the passport photograph for signs of morphing attacks, where features from multiple individuals might have been combined to create a fraudulent document. The S-MAD algorithm provides a confidence score indicating the probability that the passport image is authentic.

Subsequently, **D-MAD** is applied using the double siamese framework. This step compares the passport photograph against the captured selfie to detect potential morphing attacks through differential analysis. D-MAD provides an additional layer of security by identifying discrepancies that might indicate document tampering.

The final step involves an **EBSI wallet creation**. Based on the successful completion of all previous verification steps, the application contacts an issuer and receives a verifiable credential containing the traveler's verified identity information. This credential is cryptographically signed and stored in a local EBSI-compatible wallet, providing a secure, tamper-evident record of the pre-registration process that can later be verified by border authorities.

Upon successful completion of pre-registration, the traveler can create and manage upcoming trips within the app by specifying the intended travel date/time and the target BCP. Trips can be edited or deleted at any time, and all personal data, including trip records, is stored locally on the user's device. Additionally, the application transmits non-personal metadata, such as the BCP identifier and time window, without any personal identifiers, to the backend. This supports forecasting of expected arrivals and enables staffing optimization at BCPs ahead of traveler arrival.

III-B. Border Crossing Process Pipeline

The border crossing workflow facilitates secure data exchange between the traveler’s Pre-Registration App and the border guard’s verification system. This process preserves privacy while enabling efficient identity verification at BCPs.

The workflow begins when the traveler adds a new trip within the Pre-Registration App, specifying the intended date, time, and destination BCP. This information helps border authorities anticipate arrival patterns and manage resources effectively.

Upon arrival at the BCP, the border guard initiates the secure communication process by **generating a QR code** via the Border Guard App. This code encodes the necessary parameters to establish a WiFi Direct connection, including network credentials and security keys for the handshake process.

The traveler then **scans the QR code** using their device, which automatically extracts the connection parameters and initiates WiFi Direct pairing. The app prompts the user to grant permission before establishing the connection and transmitting any data, ensuring that consent is obtained prior to exchange.

Once permission is granted, the Pre-Registration App **transmits the pre-registration data** to the Border Guard App over the secure WiFi Direct channel. The transmitted package includes biometric verification results, biometric and passport data, and a verification offer to initiate the VC presentation flow.

The Border Guard App **receives and processes the data locally** in preparation for real-time verification. Simultaneously, the border guard **captures a live photograph** of the traveler using the device’s camera.

This newly captured image is processed through **OFIQ quality assessment** to verify compliance with the same image quality standards applied during pre-registration. Consistency in image quality supports accurate and reliable biometric comparison.

The system then performs **FaceNet-based similarity verification**, comparing the live image with both the pre-registered selfie and the passport photograph. This multi-source comparison generates similarity scores that support the verification of the traveler’s identity and aid in detecting potential fraud.

Following this, the app conducts **EBSI VC verification**, cryptographically validating the traveler’s digital credential. This step ensures the authenticity, integrity, and non-repudiation of the pre-registration data.

Finally, the Border Guard App **displays all verification results** through a dedicated user interface, presenting quality metrics, similarity scores, and cryptographic validation outcomes. This consolidated view supports informed decision-making while maintaining the necessary human oversight for secure border operations.

This comprehensive workflow ensures secure, P2P communication between devices and streamlines border crossing through a multi-layered, privacy-preserving verification process. The full sequence of both applications is illustrated in Figure 2.

Fig. 2. End-to-end workflow of the border crossing process showing the secure data exchange between the traveler’s Pre-Registration App and the Border Guard App via QR-based handshake and Wi-Fi Direct communication.

IV. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

IV-A. Application Structure

Overview. The system comprises two Android mobile applications, the *Pre-Registration App* for travelers and the *Border Guard App* for officers and two backend components: (i) a *Management Backend*, which supports expected-arrival forecasting and operational statistics, and (ii) the *External Trust and EBSI Verifiable Credential Ecosystem*, used exclusively for issuing and verifying digital credentials.

IV-A0a. Mobile Clients:

- **Pre-Registration App (traveler).** Handles MRZ and NFC reading, facial image capture, OFIQ assessment,

FaceNet-based similarity verification, S-MAD, D-MAD and local credential storage. All personal data generated during pre-registration is **stored locally** on the traveler’s device. The app also allows users to create, edit, and delete trips. For each trip, a corresponding **non-personal** metadata record is transmitted to the Management Backend. Additionally, when creating a new trip, the app verifies that no overlapping trips have been declared within the same timeslot. If a conflict is detected, the user is prevented from submitting the new trip, thus avoiding potential input errors and ensuring that border officers receive accurate information regarding expected arrivals.

- **Border Guard App (officer).** Supports secure sign-in for authorized border officers, receives the traveler’s data over a local P2P channel at the BCP, and performs on-device verification. No personal data is stored persistently. After each control interaction, the app reports a non-personal outcome (e.g., `success` or `secondary-check`) to the Management Backend for statistical analysis.

IV-A0b. Management Backend (Operations and Statistics): This backend stores only **non-personal** metadata required for operational planning and reporting. Specifically:

- **Trip Registry (non-personal).** For each registered trip, the backend stores a Unique Identifier (UID), the intended `date/time` timeslot, and the associated BCP identifier. No personal data or images are stored or transmitted.
- **Expected Arrivals Aggregation.** Computes expected arrival counts per BCP and shift based solely on non-personal trip metadata. These aggregates are made available to the Border Guard App upon login to support staffing awareness.
- **Guard authentication.** Provides user authentication and role management for the Border Guard App.
- **Control Outcomes (non-personal).** Records the result of each verification process (e.g., `success`, `secondary-check`) to support operational monitoring and retrospective analysis.

IV-A0c. External Trust & EBSI Verifiable Credential Ecosystem Components:

- **EBSI ledger.** Serves as a decentralized trust anchor, it stores an issuer’s public cryptographic keys and accreditations.
- **Issuer.** Belongs to a passport issuing authority, responsible for the issuance of the traveler’s Digital Travel Credential (DTC) during pre-registration.
- **Holder Wallet.** Integrated within the Pre-Registration App, this component receives and stores the DTC and presents it when requested during the verification process at the BCP.
- **Verifier.** Integrated into the Border Guard App, this component validates the authenticity and integrity of the presented credential.

IV-A0d. Privacy Boundary and Device-to-Device Communication: All personal data remains stored locally on the

traveler’s device and is shared only with the Border Guard App at the BCP via a secure P2P connection. The two mobile applications establish this connection through a QR-code handshake followed by WiFi Direct pairing, which enables the secure transfer of the traveler’s locally stored verification payload to the Border Guard App. No personal data is transmitted to any backend component prior to the traveler’s arrival at the border. The backend components store only non-personal metadata related to trip scheduling and control outcomes.

V. IMPLEMENTATION DETAILS

V-A. Development Environment and Dependencies

The system is implemented as two native Android applications developed using standard Android development practices and cutting-edge mobile technologies. Both applications leverage a hybrid architecture combining high-level Android frameworks with native C++ components for computationally intensive operations.

Core Development Stack: Both applications are developed in Android Studio using Kotlin as the primary programming language, targeting Android API levels 21–35 to ensure broad device compatibility. Jetpack Compose is used for declarative UI development, enabling responsive and intuitive interfaces. A minimum SDK version of 21 ensures support for devices running Android 5.0 and above.

V-B. Native Components Integration and JNI Architecture

Hybrid Architecture Overview: Both applications integrate native C++ libraries through the Android NDK (version 28.1.13356709), using CMake 3.22.1 for cross-compilation and the Java Native Interface (JNI) for runtime communication. This hybrid approach enables the deployment of sophisticated computer vision and machine learning algorithms while maintaining the flexibility and user experience advantages of native Android development.

V-B0a. CMake Build System: CMake serves as the cross-platform build system that compiles C++ source code into native libraries (`.so` files) optimized for ARM64 and ARMv7 architectures. The build configuration links multiple C++ libraries, including OpenCV, ONNX Runtime, and OFIQ, into unified native modules, automatically handling platform-specific compilation flags and dependency management.

V-B0b. JNI Bridge Architecture: The system employs Java Native Interface (JNI) to seamlessly integrate C++ native libraries with the Android applications. JNI serves as the critical runtime bridge enabling Kotlin/Java code to invoke native functions for computationally intensive operations including machine learning inference, image processing, and quality assessment.

The integrated CMake-JNI architecture enables the applications to leverage the full computational power of native libraries while maintaining the Android framework’s lifecycle management, permission system, and user interface capabilities.

V-C. Machine Learning and Computer Vision Framework

V-C0a. ONNX Runtime Integration: The system uses Microsoft’s ONNX Runtime as the primary inference engine for machine learning models.

For morphing attack detection, the system deploys three specialized ONNX models: the S-MAD model based on Inception-ResNet-V1 architecture (input size 299×299), and two D-MAD models comprising a Siamese network and ArcFace feature extractor (input size 112×112). Model loading and initialization occur asynchronously during application startup, with intelligent caching to minimize subsequent inference latency.

V-C0b. FaceNet Implementation: Face recognition capabilities are implemented using a TensorFlow Lite deployment of FaceNet, generating 128-dimensional embeddings optimized for mobile execution. The implementation includes automatic face detection using OpenCV’s cascade classifiers, followed by preprocessing steps including resize to 160×160 pixels, normalization, and tensor formatting. Similarity computation employs cosine similarity with a threshold (which was set at 0.65) for identity verification.

V-C0c. OFIQ Integration: The OFIQ assessment is implemented through direct integration of the OFIQ C++ library, providing ISO/IEC 29794-5 compliant quality evaluation. The implementation supports 26 distinct quality measures including illumination uniformity, sharpness, pose estimation, and expression neutrality. Image preprocessing includes automatic color space conversion (BGR to RGB) and bit-depth adaptation to ensure consistent quality assessment across different capture conditions.

V-D. Secure Communication Architecture

WiFi Direct Implementation: P2P communication between the two mobile applications is implemented using Android’s WiFi Direct framework, along with a custom protocol stack for secure data transmission. The connection process begins with QR code-based device discovery, followed by automatic network negotiation and the establishment of an encrypted communication channel.

The implementation accounts for Android 13+ permission requirements, including the use of `NEARBY_WIFI_DEVICES` and location access, while providing backward compatibility for earlier Android versions. Connection management features include automatic retry logic, timeout handling, and robust error recovery mechanisms to ensure reliable and uninterrupted data exchange under various network conditions.

V-E. Document Processing and NFC Integration

V-E0a. MRZ Recognition: MRZ scanning is implemented using Google’s ML Kit Text Recognition API combined with Tesseract OCR for enhanced accuracy. The implementation includes real-time camera preview with automatic document detection, perspective correction using OpenCV transforms, and multi-frame text extraction for improved reliability.

V-E0b. NFC Passport Reading: Electronic passport reading utilizes the JMRTD (Java Machine Readable Travel Documents) library for standardized data extraction. The implementation supports both BAC (Basic Access Control) and PACE (Password Authenticated Connection Establishment) protocols, with automatic fallback mechanisms for different passport chip types.

Image extraction from passport chips handles multiple formats including JPEG2000, WSQ, and standard JPEG, with specialized decoders for each format. The implementation includes robust error handling for corrupted or non-standard chip data, ensuring reliable operation across diverse passport implementations.

V-F. EBSI Verifiable Credential Ecosystem Components

The components related to the EBSI verifiable credential ecosystem comply to the v3.2 EBSI conformance testing, and follow the specifications employed by EBSI. Specifically, for the standards that are related with the data models, World Wide Web’s (W3C) Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs) v1.0 [8] and Verifiable Credentials Data Model (VCDM) v1.1 [9], Decentralized Identity Foundation’s (DIF) Presentation Exchange 2.0.0 [10]. While, in terms of protocol flows, EBSI employs specifications that are developed by the special topic group on OpenID for Verifiable Credentials (OID4VC) [11] of the OpenID Foundation, namely OpenID for Verifiable Credential Issuance (OID4VCI) draft 11 [12], and OpenID for Verifiable Presentations (OID4VP) draft 14 [13].

V-G. Performance Optimizations

V-G0a. Model Optimization: All machine learning models undergo quantization and optimization for mobile deployment. ONNX models utilize 16-bit floating-point precision where applicable, reducing memory footprint while maintaining inference accuracy. Model caching and intelligent preloading minimize cold-start latency during critical verification operations.

V-G0b. Memory Management: The applications implement sophisticated memory management strategies including bitmap recycling, native memory cleanup, and garbage collection optimization. Large image processing operations utilize streaming approaches to minimize peak memory usage, ensuring stable operation on devices with limited RAM.

V-G0c. Threading Architecture: Computationally intensive operations execute on dedicated background threads using Kotlin coroutines and Android’s threading primitives. The architecture ensures UI responsiveness while maximizing utilization of multi-core processors common in modern smartphones.

V-H. Data Privacy and Security

V-H0a. Local Data Storage: All personal data remains stored locally using Android’s secure storage mechanisms including encrypted SharedPreferences and private internal storage. Biometric templates and document images are never transmitted to external servers, ensuring complete data sovereignty for travelers.

V-H0b. Secure Communication: WiFi Direct communications employ WPA2 encryption with additional application-layer security. QR code handshakes include cryptographic tokens to prevent man-in-the-middle attacks, while data transmission protocols include integrity verification and replay attack prevention.

The system architecture ensures that sensitive personal data is only transmitted over the local P2P channel at the border crossing point, maintaining privacy while enabling efficient verification processes.

VI. DISCUSSION

VI-A. Operational Advantages

The proposed privacy-preserving border control system demonstrates significant advantages over traditional border inspection approaches through its innovative combination of mobile-first architecture and advanced biometric technologies. The system addresses three critical challenges in modern border management: processing efficiency, security assurance, and traveler privacy.

VI-A0a. Enhanced Processing Efficiency: By enabling pre-registration completion before arrival at BCPs, the system fundamentally transforms the border crossing workflow. Traditional systems require travelers to complete all verification steps upon arrival, creating bottlenecks during peak travel periods. Our approach allows travelers to perform document scanning, biometric capture, and quality assessment from their homes, reducing on-site processing time. The arrival data transmission via WiFi Direct further streamlines the border guard's workflow, presenting comprehensive verification results within seconds rather than minutes.

VI-A0b. Improved Security Through Multimodal Verification: The integration of multiple state-of-the-art verification technologies provides enhanced security compared to traditional single-point verification systems. The combination of cryptographic passport validation through NFC, advanced morphing attack detection (S-MAD and D-MAD), face recognition with FaceNet, and ISO-compliant image quality assessment through OFIQ creates multiple security layers that significantly increase the difficulty of fraudulent border crossings. This multimodal approach ensures that potential attacks targeting one verification method are detected by complementary systems.

VI-A0c. Resource Optimization and Scalability: The system enables better resource allocation at BCPs through expected arrival forecasting based on pre-registration data. Border authorities can adjust staffing levels and prepare for peak periods using anonymized trip metadata, improving operational efficiency without compromising traveler privacy. The mobile-first architecture eliminates the need for specialized hardware investments at each border crossing, enabling rapid deployment across multiple locations with minimal infrastructure requirements.

VI-B. Privacy and Security Implications

VI-B0a. Data Sovereignty and Privacy Preservation: A fundamental advantage of the proposed system is its

commitment to data sovereignty. Unlike cloud-based border control solutions that require transmission of personal data to external servers, our architecture ensures that all biometric templates, document images, and verification results remain on the traveler's device until the moment of border crossing. This approach addresses growing concerns about government surveillance and data misuse while maintaining the security requirements essential for border control.

The local processing of biometric data using on-device machine learning models ensures that sensitive information never leaves the traveler's control until explicitly shared during the border crossing process. Even during data transmission, the secure P2P channel between devices ensures that personal information is not exposed to network intermediaries or stored in backend systems.

VI-B0b. Cryptographic Security and Integrity: The integration with EBSI's VCs ensures a high level of cryptographic security and data integrity, through the use of DIDs, asymmetric key cryptography, and blockchain-based trust anchors. Verifiable credentials are digitally signed by an issuing authority using keys registered on the EBSI DID registry, which allows verifiers to authenticate the origin and that the credentials have not been tampered with. Furthermore, built on top of OAuth2.0, the OID4VC protocols enable secure, standards-based credential issuance and presentation flows.

VI-B0c. Attack Resistance and Robustness: The system demonstrates robust resistance to various attack vectors through its layered security architecture. Morphing attacks are addressed through both single and differential detection algorithms. The WiFi Direct communication protocol includes protection against man-in-the-middle attacks, while the NFC passport reading provides cryptographic validation of document authenticity.

VI-C. Technical Innovation and Contributions

VI-C0a. Mobile Edge Computing for Border Security: The successful deployment of sophisticated computer vision and machine learning algorithms on consumer smartphones represents a significant advancement in mobile edge computing applications. The system demonstrates that advanced biometric verification, previously requiring specialized hardware, can be effectively performed on standard Android devices through optimized model deployment and efficient resource management.

The integration of ONNX Runtime for model inference, combined with native C++ implementation through JNI, achieves performance levels comparable to dedicated hardware while maintaining the flexibility and user experience advantages of mobile applications. This approach opens new possibilities for deploying advanced AI capabilities in resource-constrained environments.

VI-C0b. Standardized Quality Assessment Integration: The implementation of ISO/IEC 29794-5 compliant face image quality assessment through OFIQ integration ensures that captured biometric data meets international standards before submission for verification. This proactive quality control

reduces verification failures and improves overall system reliability, addressing a common challenge in mobile biometric capture where lighting conditions and user positioning can significantly impact image quality.

VI-D. Real-World Performance Challenges and Limitations

VI-D0a. Face Recognition Performance in Uncontrolled Environments: Real-world testing of the system revealed significant challenges with face similarity verification under diverse environmental conditions. During field testing conducted outside controlled office environments, including outdoor settings and vehicle interiors (representing the primary use case scenario), face recognition similarity scores demonstrated notable degradation. The FaceNet algorithm, while performing adequately under optimal lighting conditions, showed reduced accuracy when processing images captured in suboptimal environments such as direct sunlight, shadows, or confined spaces like vehicle cabins.

To address immediate operational requirements, the similarity threshold was temporarily reduced to 65%. However, this lower threshold represents a compromise between usability and security that requires careful consideration. The reduced threshold increases the risk of false positives while still potentially rejecting legitimate users under challenging capture conditions, highlighting the need for enhanced preprocessing techniques or more robust face recognition algorithms specifically designed for varying environmental conditions.

This challenge underscores the importance of comprehensive field testing in developing mobile biometric systems and demonstrates that laboratory performance metrics may not accurately reflect real-world deployment effectiveness.

VI-D0b. Device Compatibility and Performance Variations: While the system targets broad device compatibility through minimum SDK requirements, performance variations across different smartphone models may affect user experience. Older devices with limited computational resources may experience longer processing times for machine learning inference, potentially impacting adoption rates among users with legacy hardware.

VI-D0c. Network Dependency for Critical Features: Although the system is designed for offline operation during pre-registration, certain components such as EBSI wallet verification and expected arrival reporting require network connectivity. In areas with limited connectivity, these features may be unavailable, potentially affecting the system's overall effectiveness in remote border crossing locations.

VI-E. Future Work

The development and real-world testing of this privacy-preserving border control system have revealed several promising directions for future research and development. These improvements focus on expanding platform compatibility, enhancing biometric recognition robustness, and improving system resilience in challenging network environments.

VI-E0a. Cross-Platform Mobile Development: We are actively investigating the development of an iOS version of

both applications to expand the system's accessibility across mobile platforms. One of the key factors in our initial technology selection was the cross-platform capabilities offered by Kotlin and Jetpack Compose, which provide significant advantages for multi-platform deployment with minimal additional development effort.

VI-E0b. Enhanced Face Recognition Robustness:

The environmental challenges encountered during real-world testing have highlighted the need for improved face recognition performance under varying lighting conditions. We are pursuing two complementary research directions to address these limitations. First, we are investigating sophisticated image enhancement techniques to improve input quality before FaceNet processing. Second, we are evaluating more robust face recognition algorithms that demonstrate superior performance under challenging environmental conditions, including lightweight versions of ArcFace with improved illumination invariance.

VI-E0c. EBSI Related Components: In order to remain aligned with EBSI's evolving specifications, it will be required to continuously update and maintain the EBSI related components. Additionally, the current implementation relies on a backend service-wallet for the traveler's credential management, to enhance user privacy future development will focus on transitioning to an on-device holder wallet implementation.

VI-E0d. EBSI Connectivity Resilience: The challenging network connectivity conditions commonly encountered at Border Control Points necessitate enhanced offline capabilities for the EBSI wallet verification system. We are developing a comprehensive caching and synchronization framework to maintain system functionality during network outages. The proposed caching mechanism will maintain local copies of critical EBSI verification data, including trusted issuer lists, revocation status information, and cryptographic validation keys. The system will implement intelligent cache management and background synchronization when connectivity is restored, enabling border guards to validate EBSI credentials using cached data while maintaining security guarantees.

VII. CONCLUSION

This paper presented a novel privacy-preserving border control system that fundamentally transforms traditional border crossing procedures through mobile-first architecture and advanced biometric technologies. The system successfully demonstrates that comprehensive document verification, biometric authentication, and quality assessment can be performed entirely on consumer smartphones without compromising security standards.

The key contributions of this work include the development of two Android applications supporting the complete border crossing workflow, successful integration of multiple state-of-the-art technologies including OFIQ quality assessment, S-MAD and D-MAD morphing attack detection, FaceNet face recognition, and EBSI digital identity management, and implementation of a secure peer-to-peer communication pro-

to col that ensures data sovereignty while enabling efficient verification at Border Control Points.

Real-world testing revealed both the system's potential and its challenges. While the multimodal verification approach provides enhanced security through layered authentication, face recognition performance under varying environmental conditions highlighted the need for more robust algorithms or enhanced preprocessing techniques. The temporary reduction of the similarity threshold to 65% represents a compromise that enables operational deployment while identifying areas for future improvement.

The system's architecture successfully addresses critical challenges in modern border management: reducing processing times through pre-arrival registration, enabling better resource allocation through expected arrival forecasting, and maintaining traveler privacy through local data processing and secure P2P communication. The modular design facilitates future enhancements, including cross-platform deployment to iOS devices and integration of more resilient biometric algorithms.

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REFERENCES

- [1] G. Stavropoulos, A. Kalpazidis, and K. Votis, "VehicLens: An Integrated AI System for Vehicle Classification and Occupant Analysis in Border Security Applications," SPIE Security + Defence 2025, Madrid, Spain, September 16, 2025.
- [2] M. Ferrara, A. Franco, and D. Maltoni, "The magic passport," IEEE International Joint Conference on Biometrics, pp. 1-7, 2014.
- [3] G. Borghi, N. Di Domenico, A. Franco, M. Ferrara, and D. Maltoni, "Revelio: a Modular and Effective Framework for Reproducible Training and Evaluation of Morphing Attack Detectors," IEEE Access, 2023.
- [4] G. Borghi, E. Pancisi, M. Ferrara, and D. Maltoni, "A double siamese framework for differential morphing attack detection," Sensors, vol. 21, no. 10, pp. 3466, 2021.
- [5] F. Schroff, D. Kalenichenko, and J. Philbin, "FaceNet: A Unified Embedding for Face Recognition and Clustering," IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR), pp. 815-823, 2015.
- [6] German Federal Office for Information Security (BSI), "Open Source Face Image Quality (OFIQ)," Available: <https://github.com/BSI-OFIQ/OFIQ-Project>, 2024.
- [7] European Commission, "European Blockchain Services Infrastructure (EBSI)," Digital Strategy, 2023.
- [8] W3C, "Decentralized Identifiers (DIDs) v1.0," W3C Recommendation, 19 July 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.w3.org/TR/did-1.0/>. Accessed: Sep. 30, 2025.
- [9] W3C, "Verifiable Credentials Data Model v1.1," W3C Recommendation, Mar. 3, 2022. [Online]. Available: <https://www.w3.org/TR/2022/REC-vc-data-model-20220303>. Accessed: Sep. 30, 2025.
- [10] Decentralized Identity Foundation, "Presentation Exchange v2.0.0," DIF RATIFIED specification. [Online]. Available: <https://identity.foundation/presentation-exchange/spec/v2.0.0/>. Accessed: Sep. 30, 2025.
- [11] OpenID Foundation, "OpenID for Verifiable Credentials (OpenID4VC)," OpenID Foundation Specification Overview. [Online]. Available: <https://openid.net/sg/openid4vc/>. Accessed: Sep. 30, 2025.
- [12] OpenID Foundation, "OpenID 4 Verifiable Credential Issuance 1.0," OpenID Specification. [Online]. Available: https://openid.net/specs/openid-4-verifiable-credential-issuance-1_0-11.html. Accessed: Sep. 30, 2025.
- [13] OpenID Foundation, "OpenID 4 Verifiable Presentations 1.0," OpenID Specification. [Online]. Available: https://openid.net/specs/openid-4-verifiable-presentations-1_0-14.html. Accessed: Sep. 30, 2025.